

Flowering behavior of ratoons of F₂ rice segregates

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Photoperiod-sensitive traditional indicas such as FR13A and Achra 108/1 that flower in Mar-Apr at RRS, Chinsurah (22° 58'N) can be ratooned and will flower in Oct when daylength is similar (11 h to 11 h 30 min). Few traditional varieties show similar type of behavior.

We tested crosses of FR13A, Achra 108/1, IR36, and IR50 for flowering behavior of their ratoons when sown in November.

Seeds of the crosses were sown 15 Nov 1983 and transplanted in mid-Jan

Flowering behavior of F₂ segregates and their ratoons, Chinsurah, India, 1984.

Cross	Plants (no.)	Plants flowering in Mar-Apr (no.)	Ratooned plants flowering in Oct		Plants flowering in intermediate months ^a	
			No.	%	No.	%
FR13A/Achra 108/1	106	88	44	50	44	50
FR13A/IR36	106	102	42	41	60	59
FR13A/IR50	106	103	48	41	55	53
Achra 108/1/IR36	106	96	35	36	61	63
Achra 100/1/IR50	106	102	40	39	62	61
IR36/IR50	106	106	—	—	—	—

^a Jul-Sep.

1984. Plants that flowered in Apr were ratooned at the end of May, and remaining plants in vegetative stage were uprooted. Flowering behavior of ratooned plants was recorded. Plants that flowered between Jul and Sep and

in Oct were separated (see table). Of the plants obtained from different crosses, 36-50% flowered twice and fitted the desired behavior. However, crosses between photoperiod-insensitive types failed to produce desirable plants. \mathcal{L}

Effect of salinity on rice dry matter accumulation and sodium uptake

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Soil salinity constrains rice growth in parts of many countries. It is important to identify salt-tolerant rices and criteria for salt tolerance. We evaluated eight high yielding rice varieties with known levels of salt tolerance and sensitivity to

Table 1. Effect of salinity stress on dry matter production of rice varieties at peak tillering stage, West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	Dry matter production (g/pot) at ECe (mmho/cm) of		
	3.0 (control)	8.0	12.0
CSR-1	28	27 (2)	19 (31)
CSR-6	18	11 (39)	10 (46)
CST14-2	20	15 (27)	11 (43)
CST438-1	23	17 (29)	13 (44)
CST202-2	13	8 (43)	6 (53)
CST100-1	19	12 (36)	9 (56)
Jaya	18	10 (44)	7 (68)
M1-48	14	7 (51)	9 (75)

CD at P = 0.05

Variety = 0.442 g

Salinity = 0.270 g

Variety × salinity = 0.766 g

^a Figures in parentheses indicate reduction percentage over control.

quantify dry matter accumulation and the pattern of Na⁺ uptake. The experiment was at CSSRI in Canning.

Soil salinity levels (ECe 3, 8, and 12 mmho/cm) were created by adding saline river water. The average composition (mg/litre) of river water at a salinity level of 35 mmho/cm at 25° C was Na⁺ = 7571, K⁺ = 269, Ca²⁺ = 403, Mg²⁺ = 778, Cl⁻ = 1334, SO₄²⁻ = 969, and pH = 7.8. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 18-kg porcelain pots with 6 replications. N, P, and K were applied at 120-60-60 kg/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Table 2. Effect of salinity stress on accumulation of Na⁺ by rice plants at peak tillering, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Na ⁺ accumulation (% of dry matter) at ECe (mmho/cm) of		
	3.0	8.0	12.0
CSR-1	0.21	0.29	0.36
CSR-6	0.24	0.35	0.44
CST14-2	0.23	0.27	0.41
CST438-1	0.21	0.29	0.41
CST202-2	0.31	0.38	0.46
CST100-1	0.23	0.33	0.44
Jaya	0.25	0.39	0.50
M1-48	0.27	0.61	1.15

CD at P = 0.05

Variety = 0.018% Na

Salinity = 0.011% Na

Variety × salinity = 0.031% Na.

Dry matter accumulation decreased significantly as soil salinity increased. CSR-1 (var. Damodar) had least dry matter reduction at peak tillering (Table 1). At moderate salinity (8.00 mmho/cm), dry matter reduction in CSR-1 (var. Damodar) was 2%. M-1-48 dry matter production declined 51%.

We analyzed plant tissue accumulation of Na⁺ at peak tillering. Plant tissue accumulated more Na⁺ as soil salinity increased (Table 2). Susceptible varieties accumulated the highest levels, and dry matter production decreased as tissue accumulated more Na⁺.

Results indicated that rice varieties that accumulate less Na⁺ in the shoots at peak tillering stage are more tolerant of salinity than varieties that accumulate higher amounts of Na⁺. \mathcal{L}

Azolla and NH₄NO₃ as organic and inorganic nitrogen sources for rice plants

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We compared azolla-N and NH₄NO₃-N availability to rice plants in the greenhouse. Soil, Dransfelder II, was